

Application of single-factor experimental design analysis based on variable parameters of bleach wash on Denim fabrics

Ashraful Islam^{1*}, Niloy Bhattacharjee^{2*}, Md. Iusuf Khan^{3*}, Ullas Chowdhury Mitu^{4*}, Sharmila Dutta⁵, Mohammad Mobinul Islam⁶, Tony Haldar⁷

¹Port City International University, Senior Lecturer, BFT

³Port City International University, Assistant Professor, BTE

^{2,4,5,6,7} Bachelor of Textile Engineering- Port City International University, Chattogram, Bangladesh

Abstract: This paper aims to use the bleach wash effect on denim fabrics. Denim garments are the most preferred of today's youth. From special wear to regular wear, woven denim has barged into the acceptance of kids, women, and men. However, fashion trends favor faded woven denim, which can only be achieved through apparel washing. This project work aimed to study the effect of bleach wash using bleaching powder on 100% cotton indigo-dyed woven denim apparel (jeans). Denim was washed using three parameters for instance KCI bleach concentration 5 g/l, temperature 60°C, and time for 30 minutes. It was achieved that the bleach wash method is very effective for woven denim apparel to achieve the required color depth. It was also revealed that there are massive distinguish in wash properties between bleach-washed and raw Denim. There were several tests have done in this experiment such as Dimensional Stability, Tensile strength, End/inch, Picks/inch, Yarn Count (Ne), GSM, and Hue's depth analogy.

Keywords: Denim fabric, Bleach wash, Variable bleach concentration, Changeable Temperature, different time, color fastness properties.

*Corresponding Author: Ashraful Islam

Accepted: 28 September, 2024; Published: 29 September, 2024

How to cite this article: Ashraful Islam, Niloy Bhattacharjee, Md. Iusuf Khan, Ullas Chowdhury Mitu, Sharmila Dutta, Mohammad Mobinul Islam, Tony Haldar (2024). Application of single-factor experimental design analysis based on variable parameters of bleach wash on Denim fabrics. *North American Academic Research*, 7(9), 215-227. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14545337>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2024 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Denim is a sturdy cotton twill textile in which the weft passes under two or more warp threads. This twill weaving produces the familiar diagonal ribbing of the denim that distinguishes it from cotton duck.[1] It is a characteristic of any indigo denim that only the warp threads are dyed, whereas the weft threads remain plain white. As a result of the warp-faced twill weaving, one side of the textile then shows the blue warp threads and the other side shows the white weft threads.[2] This is why blue jeans are white on the inside. This type of dyeing also creates denim's fading characteristics,

which are unique compared to every other textile. The word 'jeans' comes from the French phrase 'bleu de Genes' meaning 'the blue of Genoa'. The denim fabric originated in the French town of Nimes and owes its name to the location, which was quickly known as 'denim' abroad.[3] Spunky Genoese Navy sailors first strutted around in denim back in the 1500's but it wasn't until the 1870's in the gold rush boom that denim took off. This was when Levi Strauss – a name now synonymous with denim – created a strong style of workers pants with rivets that was quickly adopted by Californian coal miners.[4] Originally made from uncomfortable hemp, Strauss eventually discovered and started using the twilled cotton cloth that originated from the French town of Nimes, and denim, as we know it, was born.[5] For a long time, it was largely worn by workers but became popular in American Pop Culture when jeans became symbolic of protest against conformity.[6] [7]. But the trend grew and during the 1960's wearing blue jeans became more acceptable and by the 1970's they were truly established as a fashion trend. [8, 9]. Each season brings with it new cuts, features, treatments and embellishments.

Characteristics of denim fabric:

1. It is for long wearing.
2. It is hard wearing.
3. It is very strong and durable.
4. It resists snags and tears
5. It creases easily.
6. Warp yarns are colored (usually with indigo, vat, blue or Sulphur black).
7. Structure: Right hand or left-hand twill, i.e. z/s-twill of 2/1 or 3/1 construction.
8. Usually made of cotton yarns of coarser count (7s, 10s, 14s, 16s, etc.)
9. Coarser cloth (weight lies between 6-14 oz/sq. yds) and used for pant and warm jackets.
10. Rotor yarn is usually used.

1. As per weight /unit area:

- Lightweight: 4.5 to 7 oz/sq.yd
- Medium weight: 7 to 10 oz/sq.yd
- Heavyweight: 11 and above.
-

Denim is a very strong, stiff, and hard-wearing woven fabric that uses colored warp and white weft yarn. [10] But without finishing treatments, denim garments are uncomfortable to wear due to their weaving and dyeing effects. Denim is produced using very coarser yarn in both warp and weft. In addition, warp yarns are mostly dyed with indigo and sized.[11] As a result, denim is a very stiff fabric and hard. So, denim apparel needs a finishing treatment to make them soft, smooth, and comfortable.[12] Washing practice is the best choice to achieve these purposes. Bangladesh is a textile-based country. Denim apparel (jeans) is being produced with other apparel to meet its demand in the competitive market of the world.[13] Today's youth are very fashion concern. It is very challenging to meet their quick change of current demands. At present, the demand for denim apparel with a faded look is increasing rapidly. Various types of washing have been used on denim apparel to give them a used look.[14] Common washing practices are bleach wash, acid wash, enzyme wash, normal wash, bleach with stone wash, etc. Among the washing methods, the bleach wash is the widely used method in the washing industry.[15] It has been investigated by the many researchers that bleaching treatment is successful for achieving desirable color shade and soft hand feels of cotton denim apparel.[16] That's why bleach wash with bleaching powder is chosen for this project work. Bleach wash: Bleach wash is the process that is done by using a strong oxidative bleaching agent. In bleach wash, bleach chemical is used in water while washing in a tumble washer. [17] Strict washing time is a requirement with such a wash, otherwise, the garment may be overbleached and the color cannot be reversed.

Process Flowchart of Bleach Washing:

The basic steps of denim bleach washing are as follows:

Research Methodology

Materials:

1. Denim indigo color, Composition–100% Cotton fabrics, GSM–352
2. Indigo color, Composition–95% Cotton,5 % Elastane, GSM–325
3. Denim black color, Composition–65% Cotton+25 % Polyester + 10 % Elastane, GSM, 290

There are 3 types of fabrics were used in that experiment.

Machine and Equipment: The bleaching process was done at our Port City International University of dyeing and finishing laboratory. The list of Machines and equipment were used which is given below;

1. Side Loading Garments washing machine,
2. Hydro extractor machine,
3. Small dryer machine,
4. Tear tester,
5. Crock meter,
6. Pilling tester,
7. GSM cutter,
8. Electric balance,
9. Greyscale and,
10. Lightbox

Chemicals and Auxiliaries: Desizing agent, Soda ash, Alpha beta-amylase, Anti-back staining agent, Acetic acid, KCI bleach, Neutralizing agent (Sodium meta bi-sulphate), and Softener were used. These chemicals were collected from Tai Scientific local dyes and chemicals shops at Anderkillia in Chittagong.

Recipe: For bleach wash treatment:

Variable KCI Concentration (gm): 200,300,400,500 gm

Changeable Temp ($^{\circ}\text{C}$): 45,50,55,60 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)

Differentiate Time (min): 20,25,30,35 min.

Water = 500liter

Caustic Soda (NaOH) = 2% OWF

Soda Ash = 2% OWF

Stabilizer = 2.5m/liter.

For hot wash, Temp= 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Time = 5minute.

Bath Drop.

For neutralization,

Acetic acid = 2ml/liter.

Temp = Room temperature.

Time = 5minute.

The working procedure are given bellow in step by step—

Step 01:

- A lot size of 1.2kg garments (denim) is considered.
- Load the machine with water at liquor ratio of 1:10
- Switch is on for running the machine.
- Add De-sizing agent to the liquor @ 3gm/l
- Start steam supply to raise the temperature up to 60oc
- Continue the process for 20 min.
- Drop the liquor.

Step 02:

- A lot size of 1.2 kg garments (denim) is considered.
- Load the machine with water at liquor ratio of 1:10
- Switch is on for running of machine.
- Add caustic soda to the liquor @ 2%
- Add Bleaching agent (Hypochlorous) to the liquor @ 5 ml/l
- Add stabilizer to the liquor @ 2.5 ml/l
- Add soda ash to the liquor @2%
- Start steam supply to raise the temperature up to 80oc
- Continue process for 70 minutes
- Drop the liquor.

Step 03:

- A lot size of 1.2kg garments (denim) is considered.
- Load the machine with water at liquor ratio of 1:9
- Add sodium hyposulphite@ 3gm/l
- Switch is on for running of machine.
- Start steam supply to raise the temperature up to 60oc
- Continue this process for 5 min

- Drop the liquor

Step 04:

- A lot size of 1.2kg garments is considered.
- Load the machine with water at liquor ratio of 1:5
- Start machine running.
- Add acetic acid to the liquor @2ml/l
- Add softener @1gm/l
- Start steam supply to raise the temperature up to 60oc
- Continue this process for 5 min.
- Drop the liquor.
- Unload the garments.

Step 05:

- Hydro extraction the garments to remove wash of excess water from the washed garments.

Step 06:

- Load the garments
- Set Temperature 750C to 850C
- Time @ 35 to 40 minutes for hot dry
- Time @ 10 minutes for cold dry

Precaution of washing

1. Measurement of chemical should be taken carefully.
2. Concentration, time, temperature should be maintained properly for uniform bleach action.
3. Proper neutralization after bleaching.
4. Proper making the samples for various concentration, time, temperature.
5. Proper drying should be maintained.
6. Wash hands frequently to reduce the risk of exposure to blood borne diseases.
7. Wear gloves if there is even a possibility you might have contact with another person's body fluids.
8. After the removal of gloves or after exposure to blood or other potentially infectious materials, wash hands with antibacterial soap.
9. Wear gloves once and discard; do not attempt to wash and reuse.
10. Clothing or supplies contaminated with body fluids should be placed in doubled plastic bags and tied.

Bleach wash

Initially, the fabrics were cut in A4 size samples before and put onto the side-loading garments washing machine.[18] The machine was already spotless then the required chemicals and auxiliaries were added the chemicals that remained on the machine from the previous bath can be washed out the chemical ratio that was required for the number of fabrics was calculated that are going to be put on the bath. Then the fabrics put on the bath and start desizing for 10 minutes with the required chemicals. After desizing, bought out the fabrics from the machine and rinse washed the fabrics. Again, the fabrics put on the bath with the addition of enzyme, acetic acid, and anti-back staining agent and ran the machine for 15min.[19] After that again rinse washed the fabrics for 2-3min. The fabrics were put on the bath again with the addition of KCI bleach and ran the bath at 3 different concentrations, Temperatures, and Times to get 3 shades. Then bought out the fabrics from the bath and put them on the hydro-extractor machine to absorb the excess water from the machine. After that, the fabrics were put on the drying machine at 80°C to dry the fabrics.

Washing condition

Variable (KCI) bleach Concentration: Single factor Experiment design analysis based on variable blech concentration which is given below in Table 1.

Variable KCI Concentration (gm)	Temp (°C)	Time (min)
200 gm	55	35
300 gm		
400 gm		
500 gm		

In this above experimental analysis, we assume the temperature at 55 °C and time for 35 minute and just variable concentration from 200 to 500. After bleach wash process done by side loading garments washing machine. We found the light shade of bleached sample.

Variable Temperature (°C): Single factor Experiment design analysis based on variable Temperature which is given below in Table 2.

Variable Temp (°C)	Suitable bleach Concentration (gm)	Time (min)
45	500	35
50		
55		
60		

In this above experimental analysis, we got the best KCI Bleach concentration is 500 gm just variable tempera- ture of 45-60 (°C) and fixed time for 35 minutes. After bleaching wash process has done by side loading gar- ments washing machine. we found the medium shade of bleached sample.

Variable Time (min): Single factor Experiment design analysis based on variable Time which is given below in Table 3.

Variable Time (min):	Suitable Concentration (gm)	Best Temp (°C)
20	500	50
25		
30		
35		

In this above experimental analysis, we got the suitable Bleach concentration is 500 gm and suitable temp at 50 °C, just variable time from 45 to 60 (°C). After bleaching wash has done by side loading garments washing machine. We found the Dark shade of the bleached sample.

Optimum data analysis: Effects of best washing process of bleach fabrics which are given below in Table 4.

Suitable bleach Concen- tration (gm)	Suitable Temp (°C)	Suitable Time (min)
500	50	20

Result and discussion

Effect of bleach wash on denim indigo color fabrics: We fixed the temperature at 55 °C and time for 35 minutes and just variable concentration from 200 to 500. After the bleach wash process is done by side loading garments washing machine.

We found the before and after wash samples which are shown below in figure 1.

Fig. 1: Before Wash and after wash of bleach wash

Effect of bleach wash on Dark indigo color fabrics: we got the best KCl Bleach concentration is 500 gm just variable temperature from 45-60 (°C) and fixed time for 35minutes. After bleaching wash process has done by side loading garments washing machine.

We found the medium shade of bleached sample which is shown below in figure 2.

Fig. 2: Before Wash and after wash of bleach wash

Effect of bleach wash on Denim black color: In this above experimental analysis, we got the suitable Bleach concentration is 500 gm and suitable temp at 50 °C, just variable time from 45 to 60 (°C). After bleaching wash is done by side-loading garments washing machine.

we found the Dark shade of bleached sample which are shown below in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Before Wash and after wash of bleach wash

Effect of bleach wash and softening on fabric specification:

The table shows that the de-sizing, bleaching a softening imparts frequent changes in the fabric properties. It has been found that, during these selective processing, the value of fabric surface density has declined. The Ends per Inch (EPI) and Picks per Inch (PPI) increased to a lower degree. The Shrinkage property has been found to decrease, most significantly in a warped way which are given below in Table 5.

Bleaching stages		EPI	PPI	Warp count, Ne	Weft count, Ne	Shrinkage (%)
Before wash		78	54	10	11	
After wash	Sample 1	76	49	8	10	L=5.4 W=0.6
	Sample 2	75	52	8	10	L=6.5 W=1.5
	Sample 3	74	49	8	10	L=6.5 W=1.5

This effect is generally greater in the warp direction compared to the weft. This is known as relaxation shrinkage. EPI (Ends per Inch) and PPI (Picks per Inch) were increased than untreated denim garments due to this relaxation shrinkage.

Effect of bleach wash on fabric GSM: After bleaching wash, GSM also declined which are given below in Table 6.

Sample Number	Before wash	After wash
Sample 1	352	348
Sample 2	325	318
Sample 3	290	285

Shrinkage Test:

$$\text{Shrinkage \%} = \frac{\{(\text{length of fabric before wash}) - (\text{length of fabric after wash})\}}{(\text{length of fabric before wash})} \times 100$$

Example,

Length of fabric before wash = 35 cm

Length of fabric after wash = 33 cm

Now, Shrinkage % = $\{(35-33)/ 35\} \times 100$

= 5.7%

Here, Shrinkage is 5.7%. It is clear from the table that, sample 3 has more shrinkage % behavior. We found the maximum shrinkage percentage in the third sample. There were no spandex yarn uses to make the fabrics and the GSM (290) is beneath than another samples, which are given below in Table 7.

Samples	Before wash (Inches)	After wash (Inches)	Shrinkage (%)
1	35	33	5.7
2	35	33.3	5.15
3	35	33.12	5.37

Effect on Color fastness to washing: Colorfastness to washing means, a specimen of the textile, in contact with one or two specified adjacent fabrics, is mechanically agitated under described conditions of time and temperature in a soap solution, then rinsed and dried. The change in color of the specimen and the staining of the adjacent fabric are assessed with the grey scales. We have used 3 different types of composition and colored fabrics, and fastness to wash result which is shown by table 8.

SN	Before wash Color	After wash Color Change
1	Bleach Sample 5	4
2	Bleach Sample 5	4/5
3	Bleach Sample 5	5

Tear strength test

it shows that after washing, the tear strength value is higher for sample 2 rather than other samples. This is because the amount of 2 spandex yarn in these fabrics is higher than other samples and the GSM of sample 1 is higher as well (352).

Fig: Tensile tester

Table 9 Tear strength test result

Shade	Bleaching stages	Sample 1 (kgf/cm)	Sample 2 (kgf/cm)	Sample 3 (kgf/cm)
Light	Before wash	3.68	1.95	1.95
	After wash	4.06	3.48	1.76
Medium	Before wash	3.68	1.95	1.95

	After wash	3.55	3.7	1.84
Dark	Before wash	3.68	1.95	1.95
	After wash	3.12	1.90	1.74

Conclusion

The bleaching and softening treatment has a great influence on the mechanical and color properties of denim fabric. The fading effect can be increased by the bleaching but bleaching also reduces the fabric weight, tensile strength, and seam strength which might reduce the serviceability of the garments. So, an optimum bleaching action is required to get the required fading effect and softness without compensating for some important properties of denim. Finally, in denim washing our country has a bright future due to the widespread market of denim garments. We need a thorough knowledge of the denim treatment process and also on the fashion going around the world. This project will be a guideline for those who are interested in the sector. pioneer in the field of hand washing. We believe that this project will be a guideline for the washing plants in understanding and doing various treatments.

References

- [1]. Wang, M., Development and evaluation of digital denim technology. 2020: North Carolina State University.
- [2]. Peng, X. and J. Zhou, Double-faced shading effect digital jacquard fabric with a weft-backed and warp-wadded structure. *Textile Research Journal*, 2023. 93(3-4): p. 795-806.
- [3]. Annapoorani, S., Introduction to denim, in *Sustainability in denim*. 2017, Elsevier. p. 1-26.
- [4]. Downey, L., *Levi Strauss and Co*. 2007: Arcadia Publishing.
- [5]. Bach, M.S., *She Has Good Jeans: A History of Denim as Womenswear*. 2018.
- [6]. Davis, F., *Fashion, culture, and identity*. 1994: University of Chicago Press.
- [7]. Wohlmann, A., *Aged young adults: Age readings of contemporary American novels and films*. 2014: transcript Verlag.
- [8]. Steele, V., *Anti-fashion: the 1970s*. *Fashion Theory*, 1997. 1(3): p. 279-295.
- [9]. Jeon, M., *Denim Deconstructed; Deconstructing the Notion of Denim Through Avant-Garde Methods*. 2024, Auckland University of Technology.
- [10]. Didar, S.A., et al., Development of different denim effect on knitted fabric and comparative analysis with conventional woven denim on the basis of physical and dimensional properties. *Research Journal of Engineering Sciences*, ISSN, 2015. 2278: p. 9472.
- [11]. Uddin, M.G., Indigo ring dyeing of cotton warp yarns for denim fabric. *Chemical and Materials Engineering*, 2014. 2(7): p. 149-154.
- [12]. Uren, N. and A. Okur, Analysis and improvement of tactile comfort and low-stress mechanical properties of denim fabrics. *Textile Research Journal*, 2019. 89(23-24): p. 4842-4857.
- [13]. Paul, R., *Denim and jeans: an overview*. *Denim*, 2015: p. 1-11.
- [14]. Samanta, K., S. Basak, and S. Chattopadhyay, Environmentally friendly denim processing using water-free technologies, in *Sustainability in denim*. 2017, Elsevier. p. 319-348.
- [15]. Khondoker, B., et al., A comparative study between conventional & sustainable wash by the application EIM software & wash cost: an approach of environmental sustainability aspects. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 2024: p. 1-38.
- [16]. Dipti, C., A Comparative Study of Ultraviolet Protection on Treated & Untreated Denim. *International Journal of Engineering Development and Research*, 2018. 6(3): p. 433-443.
- [17]. Reinhardt, G. and G. Borchers, 16 Application of Bleaching Detergent Formulations. *Handbook of detergents, part E: applications*, 2008. 141: p. 375.

- [18]. Raduta, R., Design for dissemination of a low cost washing machine. 2008, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- [19]. Ahmed, M., M. Ahmed, and M. Hassan, An explanation of bleach wash on denim cotton fabrics. J Text Eng Fash Technol, 2021. 7: p. 87-90.

Author Photo(s) and details:

Ashraful Islam,
t2ashraful@gmail.com
Senior Lecturer, Fashion Design and Technology
Port City International University

Niloy Bhattacharjee,
niloybhattacharjee_bte21d@portcityedu.bd
Port City International University

Md. Iusuf Khan
iusufkhan50@gmail.com
Assistant Professor, BTE
Port City International University

Ullas Chowdhury Mitu ,
ullaschowdhurymitu_bte21d@portcity.edu.bd
Port City International University

Sharmila Dutta
sharmiladutta577@gmail.com
Port City International University

Mohammad Mobinul Islam
mobinulislam118859@gmail.com
Port City International University

Tony Haldar
tonyhalder2@gmail.com
Port City International University

